

USE OF EXPERIMENTAL PLACES IN THE STUDY OF PLANTS IN BOTANICAL CLASSES

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Abstract

The study of botany takes one and a half academic years. This allows it to be studied for two fall and one spring seasons, to conduct experiments and observations in the summer study area, and to be used for summer assignments in nature.

Key words: Plants, morphology, anatomy, physiology, ecology, systematics, geography, microbiology, agronomy.

The content of botany is very diverse, it includes elements of plant morphology, anatomy, physiology, ecology, systematics, geography, microbiology, agronomy. The subject is taught in grades VI-VII and aims to provide students with a general knowledge of plants and flora. This knowledge is necessary to understand that plants play an extremely important role in nature and in the national economy. Without them, it is impossible to use and process plant resources on a scientific basis. The general structure of the botany course has been tested at the school for decades and has largely justified itself [1,3].

In Grades VI-VII, students gain a general understanding of the integrity of plants through observations and simple experiments.

After an introduction to the importance of plants in human life and the national economy, as well as their place in nature, basic information about natural science as a science is given. The students then focus on the flowering plant and its organs. The use of seeds of flowering plants and fruits in early autumn allows us to see how well they are adapted to propagation [5,6].

The study of the cell focuses on its vital skills, and the tissues are gradually examined through each organ of the plant.

Subsequent topics in science include plant organs, roots and leaves; the study of their microscopic structure and function is scheduled for the fall. Students will learn about metabolism and the diversity of organic matter, as well as the respiration and nutrition of plants. In this regard, basic information about the water, mineral heat and air regime of plants is given.

Vegetative reproduction is studied after the topic of "Stem", which is entirely appropriate. This is because vegetative propagation takes place mainly through

underground and aboveground branches, twigs, and buds, and only some plants reproduce through buds on the leaves and roots. Issues related to the reproduction of plants by seeds are studied in the "Flower".

The last topic, "Plant Integrity," repeats, summarizes, and concludes the study of the entire flowering plant.

In a botany class, which is rich in a wide variety of materials, it is important to determine what students' mastery is basic, necessary, and secondary.

Of course, the most important thing in the study of nature is to know that plants play a very important role. They enrich the air with oxygen. Creates the organic matter necessary for all living things.

In the process of teaching botany, students gain knowledge for the first time about the cell structure of organisms, metabolism, existence, formation of organic matter necessary for life, sexual reproduction, development of the organic world, classification of organisms.

Students will be introduced to basic skills: working with a microscope, preparing drugs, identifying morphological, biological and systematic features, conducting experiments. They will be able to record observations and other skills.

The main feature of botany is its ability to study natural materials, living plants. Plants are ubiquitous and can be observed on trips and collected in forests, fields and gardens. Dried plants are easy to prepare for the whole winter [3,4,6].

You can grow a variety of plants in the experimental area near the school, in the corner of wildlife, in the classroom. All of this allows for the use of living organisms in teaching, with hands-on activities and the use of visual aids.

In the process of teaching botany, students acquire theoretical knowledge, and while working in the field of teaching practice, they acquire teaching and practical skills.

The complex knowledge gained from the study of plant organs and living plants allows teachers to see the organism as a whole, in relation to the function of each organ, and finally in the development of the plant, its organs and the whole plant world. They teach.

All this, together with the explanation of the materiality of the vital processes that take place in plants and the nature that surrounds them, forms the basis of a dialectical-materialist understanding of the world.

Constant contact with nature and plants allows you to carry out aesthetic education, to learn to see beauty, to create beauty in work and in the environment around you, and to do beautiful work. At the same time, students learn to understand the plant world, love nature and protect it.

Exploring wild plants teaches students to explore nature. This section can be limited to the first year and when the land area is insufficient, only the most necessary so-called "living-herbarium" flowering plants planting and transplanting, Darwin field, root system growth monitoring boxes.

In some schools, the pre-school space is not fully utilized and some are left undeveloped. It can be used as an ornamental garden with curved corridors from vacant or specially planted green areas, and can be used to expand the natural sciences department [2,5,6].

To teach students to distinguish plants in nature, wild plants should also be labeled.

These little evergreens are super-easy to grow and will look good with almost no care. Useful, edible and beautiful flowering plants brought from travel can be planted in the field to cultivate them.

The nature of planting and cultivating in nature requires its own configuration. It is important to carry out the planting of cultivated plants and cultivated wild plants, and experiments with wild plants are carried out on flat stalks and furrows.

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